

A PRACTICAL APPROACH FOR THE FATIGUE LIFE ESTIMATION OF HYBRID JOINTS THROUGH TESTING AND NUMERICAL SIMULATIONS

C. Bagni¹, A. Halfpenny¹, M. Hill¹ & A. Tarasek²

Nowadays, lightweight structures are essential to achieve higher efficiency of battery electric vehicles, and to support the development of greener ways of transportation. Hybrid joints, along with the use of lightweight materials and design optimisation, are one of the possible ways to obtain lightweight components and they are becoming increasingly popular in the transportation industry. The term ‘hybrid joint’ is commonly used to identify a connection where adhesive bonding and traditional joining techniques, such as spot welds and rivets, are used in conjunction with the aim of combining and exploiting the advantages of the individual joining techniques. To optimise the design of hybrid joints and minimise the risk of in-service fatigue failures, the transportation industry needs efficient, robust, and easy-to-use approaches for the modelling and fatigue life estimation of hybrid joints. Furthermore, the fatigue performance of hybrid joints is influenced by several factors, such as material and thickness of the jointed sheets, type of adhesive and surface preparation of the adherends, as well as type, size and quality of the mechanical joints. Therefore, it is strongly recommended to obtain bespoke Stress-Life (SN) curve parameters from testing of hybrid joint specimens, representative of the joints in the production parts.

To answer the needs highlighted above, this work presents a practical approach for estimating the fatigue life of hybrid joints that can be easily adopted by companies in the transportation industry.

Keywords: Hybrid joints; Fatigue life prediction; Finite element analysis; Stress-life parameters

INTRODUCTION

Lightweight structures are essential to achieve higher efficiency of battery electric vehicles, and to support the development of greener ways of transportation. Amongst the different options to reduce the weight of components, the transportation industry is showing an increasing interest in the use of hybrid joints. ‘Hybrid joint’ is the term that commonly refers to a connection where adhesive bonding is combined with traditional joining techniques, such as spot welds and rivets, with the aim of maximising the advantages of the individual joining techniques. Adhesives have several advantages compared to traditional joining techniques, amongst these are their reduced weight and the ability to join dissimilar materials, such as metals and composites.

The general agreement about the benefits of hybrid joints over traditional mechanical joints emerges quite clearly from the literature review carried out by Abdel Wahab [1]. This literature review mainly highlighted that hybrid joints have better mechanical properties and fatigue performance compared to traditional joining techniques. Furthermore, it was shown that the addition

¹Hottinger Bruel & Kjaer UK Ltd, Rotherham, S60 5WG, United Kingdom

²NIO Performance Engineering Ltd, Begbroke Hill, OX5 1PF, United Kingdom

of traditional mechanical joints to an adhesive joint can have an opposite effect. For example, the addition of spot welds reduces the fatigue performance of the joint, while the addition of rivets has the beneficial effect of controlling and slowing down the crack propagation in the adhesive. Moroni [2] observed that hybrid joints (clinch-bonded and self-piercing rivet (SPR)-bonded) show better fatigue performance than the joints made using the single joining techniques only below a certain load. Furthermore, Moroni stated that the superior performance of the hybrid joints under lower loads was due to the presence of the mechanical joints (clinch or SPRs) controlling and slowing down the crack propagation. Finally, Moroni observed that a sudden loss of stiffness of the joint corresponded to the failure of the adhesive. Wu et al. [3], by studying the displacement evolution during the tests, observed that hybrid joints generally show a two-stage failure: a first stage where the crack(s) initiates and propagates in the adhesive layer followed by a second stage where one or more cracks nucleates around the rivets and propagates in the base material. The superior fatigue performance of hybrid joints over the individual joining techniques was also observed by Sun et al. [4] for SPR-adhesive joints with various thickness and material combinations and by Yang et al. [5] for friction SPR-adhesive joints. Lai and Pan [6], instead, investigated the fatigue behaviour of ultrasonic spot weld (USW)-bonded and the corresponding joints made using the individual joining techniques. Their investigation showed that the fatigue performance of the hybrid and the adhesive-only joints was similar and considerably higher than that of the USW-only joints. Different failure mechanisms were also observed between low-cycle to high-cycle loading conditions, for both adhesive and hybrid joints. Al-Samhan and Darwish [7] confirmed, using finite element (FE) analyses, that hybrid (spot welds + adhesive) lap-shear joints have higher strength compared to simple spot weld lap-shear joints. Furthermore, it was observed that hybrid joints with square edge bond-lines are weaker than hybrid joints with spew fillet bond-lines. A few years later, Al-Samhan [8] by modelling riveted-bonded joints observed that an increase in bond thickness has a positive effect on the strength of the joint. Nevertheless, Al-Samhan acknowledged that the bond-lines should be produced as thin as possible to avoid significant deformation of the adhesive. Finally, Al-Samhan found that the combination of adhesive and rivets increases the strength of the joints by balancing the stresses in joints with dissimilar thicknesses.

In the past two decades, a wide range of FE modelling approaches have been used to investigate the static and fatigue behaviour of hybrid joints (see for example [7], [8], Sadowski et al. [9], Sadowski and Zarzeka-Raczkowska [10], and Fricke and Vallée [11]). Unfortunately, most of the modelling approaches proposed or used in the literature are not suitable for complex geometries (e.g., automotive body-in-white models), but only for the analysis of simple specimen-like geometries. In particular, the use of plane stress/plane strain two-dimensional elements and solid elements, commonly found in the literature, is a non-viable option or it could produce models that are computationally too onerous. An approach to estimate the fatigue performance of adhesively bonded and hybrid joints suitable for the analysis of full-body structures was proposed by Heyes et al. [12]. This approach included an FE meshing strategy similar to those commonly used by automotive manufacturers. However, the proposed method did not allow for finite fatigue life estimations.

To be able to improve and optimise the design of structures joined using hybrid techniques and reduce the risk of in-service fatigue failures, the transportation industry needs efficient, robust, and easy-to-use approaches for the modelling and fatigue life estimation of hybrid joints. To address these needs, this paper proposes a pragmatic approach that can be easily adopted by companies in the transportation industry and that allow the fatigue life estimation of hybrid joints.

NUMERICAL SIMULATION

This Section introduces two methodologies for the fatigue life estimation of hybrid joints that companies in the transportation industry can easily adopt. FE modelling guidelines requiring relatively small modifications to the FE modelling strategies currently used, particularly in the automotive industry, are also suggested. These guidelines allow the generation of reasonably mesh insensitive models that are not computationally too onerous, and that do not require congruent meshes. Furthermore, it is also briefly described how fatigue life estimations of hybrid joints can be performed using standard nCode DesignLife fatigue analysis tools and the results from the FE analysis. Finally, a convergence study of the FE models obtained using the proposed guidelines is also presented.

First method

The first method is based on the simplifying assumption of neglecting the life of the mechanical joints after the failure of the adhesive. According to this assumption, the hybrid joint is treated as a purely adhesive joint and the overall life of the hybrid joint is assumed to coincide to the life of the adhesive. The joint can be modelled by using mid-surface linear shell elements for the adherends and linear solid elements for the adhesive, connected using ‘bonded contacts’ (or similar tools, depending on the FE software used). Since the adherends are modelled using mid-surface shell elements, the adhesive is modelled with a larger thickness than in the physical joint. Therefore, the elastic modulus of the adhesive may need to be corrected to account for the larger thickness and retain the real stiffness of the joint.

It is well known that adhesives are strong under shear loading, but weak under normal loading (also called peel or opening loading). Therefore, the proposed method assumes that the peel stress is the main source of damage in the adhesive and uses this to predict the fatigue damage and fatigue life of the joint. In order to recover the peel stresses on the bond-line in a reasonably mesh independent manner, linear shell elements with membrane behaviour only are attached through ‘bonded contacts’ to the free faces of the solid elements modelling the adhesive (FIGURE 1) and the peel stresses are recovered from the centroid of the membrane shell elements. The membrane shell elements have the same material properties of the adhesive and a negligible thickness (e.g. 10^{-6} mm) to ensure they do not affect the behaviour of the joint. Finally, the use of ‘bonded contacts’ between shell and solid elements allows for non-congruent meshes.

If it is deemed necessary to try to replicate the effect (either positive or negative) of the mechanical joints on the fatigue performance of the adhesive, the mechanical joints can be added to the FE model. In this case, the mechanical joints can be modelled either by using linear solid elements or the modelling guidelines recommended in the nCode DesignLife Theory Guide [13] for spot welds (e.g. beam elements, area contact method (ACM) or penta solid elements). However, this might introduce some contact issues where the solid elements, used to model the mechanical joints, share faces and edges with both solid elements (adhesive) and shell elements (adherends). Therefore, this option must be treated with caution.

By using the peel stresses (recovered at the centroid of the membrane shell elements) as an input, together with materials’ properties, load history and fatigue parameters obtained through testing, life/damage estimations can then be easily performed using the standard DesignLife SN Analysis Engine. An example of a fatigue analysis workflow using nCode DesignLife is illustrated in FIGURE 2.

FIGURE 1 Example of the proposed modelling strategy applied to a lap-shear specimen, with the adherends and the mechanical joints in grey and the adhesive in cyan. The mechanical joints are excluded from the model.

FIGURE 2 Example of fatigue analysis workflow using nCode DesignLife.

Second method

The previous method can be extended to consider the life of the hybrid joint as the sum of the lives of the adhesive and of the mechanical joints, by adding a further step. This second step assumes that the adhesive has completely failed and no longer contributes to the behaviour of the joint. The load is therefore carried solely by the mechanical joints. The purpose of this second step is to predict the fatigue life of the mechanical joints only and it can be performed as a standard spot welded/riveted joints fatigue analysis as illustrated in the nCode DesignLife Theory Guide [13].

This second method has the advantage over the first method of producing more realistic fatigue life predictions. However, it has the disadvantage of requiring higher modelling and computational efforts. Therefore, the most appropriate method must be chosen on a case-by-case basis after the costs and benefits are carefully evaluated.

Convergence study

A convergence study of the FE modelling strategy described above in the first method was performed for both lap-shear (LS) and coach-peel (CP) geometries. ANSYS software was used for this activity. The adherends were modelled as a generic structural steel, the adhesive was modelled as a generic epoxy resin as defined in ANSYS material library, while the mechanical joints were excluded from the model. The LS specimen had the following sizes: overall length = 370 mm, overlap length = 30 mm, width = 50 mm, adherends thickness = 2 mm and adhesive thickness = 0.5 mm. The CP specimen had the following sizes: overall length = 130.5 mm, overlap length = 25 mm, width = 60 mm, adherends thickness = 2 mm and adhesive thickness = 0.5 mm. Finally, for both geometries a unit load was applied.

The initial meshes had the adhesive modelled as one single layer of solid elements and the membrane shell elements with the same size as the solid elements. Four mesh refinements of the solid elements were subsequently performed by doubling the number of layers of solid elements at each refinement and keeping the mesh of the membrane shell elements constant. FIGURE 3 and FIGURE 4 show the results (peel stresses at the centroid of both membrane shell elements and solid elements) of the FE analyses, using the initial mesh and the subsequent two mesh refinements, for lap-shear and coach-peel specimens, respectively. As expected, for both lap-shear and coach-peel geometries, all models predicted the highest peel stresses to be in the adhesive along the bond-line, and approximately in the same location, for both solid and membrane shell elements, independent of the mesh refinement. The results of the mesh refinement are graphically summarised in FIGURE 5, and they show that wrapping the free faces of the solid elements modelling the adhesive with membrane shell elements, is a valid solution to recover the peel stresses from the solid elements with a good degree of mesh insensitivity. In fact, while the maximum peel stress calculated at the centroid of the solid elements increased at each mesh refinement, the maximum peel stress calculated at the centroid of the membrane shell elements remained reasonably constant.

FIGURE 3 Graphic representation of the peel stresses in the lap-shear model evaluated at the centroid of the solid elements (a, c and e) and of the membrane shell elements (b, d, and f) for the starting mesh (a and b), the first (c and d) and the second (e and f) mesh refinement. The red arrows indicate the elements with the maximum peel stress.

FIGURE 4 Graphic representation of the peel stresses in the coach-peel model evaluated at the centroid of the solid elements (a, c and e) and of the membrane shell elements (b, d and f) for the starting mesh (a and b), the first (c and d) and the second (e and f) mesh refinement. The red arrows indicate the elements with the maximum peel stress.

FIGURE 5 Variation of the maximum peel stress with the size of the solid elements used to model the adhesive: (a) lap-shear and (b) coach-peel.

PHYSICAL TESTING AND FATIGUE PARAMETER GENERATION

It is recognised that there are various factors influencing the performance of hybrid joints, such as:

- material type of the adhesive and of the adherends,
- thickness of the adhesive and of the adherends,
- surface preparation of the adherends,
- adhesive spew,
- type and quality of the mechanical joints,
- size and distribution of the mechanical joints.

Consequently, the use of bespoke fatigue parameters obtained through physical testing of specimens representative of the production parts and processes, is recommended to achieve more accurate and reliable fatigue life predictions. This Section introduces a test-based process to obtain bespoke fatigue parameters of the hybrid joints which are readily usable in nCode DesignLife. It is worth highlighting that the proposed test-based process is specific to the materials, thicknesses, geometry (lap-shear or coach-peel), joining processes as well as the FE meshing strategy and the constitutive model used within the FE software adopted by the user. From a mathematical point of view, the joint model, f_j , obtained through this process can be generically expressed as:

$$N = f_j(S) \quad (1)$$

where N is the fatigue life and S is a stress quantity (e.g., peel stress range) which is estimated through FE analysis using the constitutive model, f_c , implemented in the adopted FE software, as follows:

$$S = f_c(L) \quad (2)$$

where L is the applied load.

The whole approach presented in this paper is based on the concept of similitude. Therefore, it is essential that not only the tested specimens are as representative as possible of the joints in the production parts, but also that the meshing strategy and the constitutive model used to derive the joint model(s) coincide with those used to model and design the production components.

When fatigue parameters are generated from physical test data it is important to identify the most appropriate failure criterion. Three possible failure criteria are:

- **Specimen separation.** When the test stops either because the specimen is physically separated or because a maximum allowable displacement, set to avoid damaging the test equipment, is reached. This last condition can leave the specimen physically intact, but with significant cracks. This failure criterion does not require additional data analysis, but it is inherently non-conservative.
- **Crack initiation.** The detection of crack initiation is generally time-consuming and heavily dependent on the skills, experience and opinion of the individual performing the process. Furthermore, this failure criterion could be over-conservative.
- **Stiffness drop.** This is based on the evolution of the specimen stiffness during the test, as described below in more detail. This failure criterion is more flexible as the stiffness drop value used as failure criterion can be chosen to represent the most suitable failure event (e.g. first visible crack, crack of a certain length, minimum allowable residual life, etc.).

A reduction in the specimen stiffness during a fatigue test is related to the initiation and propagation of one or more cracks in the specimen.

The stiffness of a specimen is defined as:

$$K(N) = \frac{\Delta F}{\Delta u(N)} \quad (3)$$

where ΔF is the applied load range (constant in constant amplitude load tests) and $\Delta u(N)$ is the displacement range (variable with the number of cycles, N , during crack propagation) defined as follows:

$$\Delta F = F_{max} - F_{min} \quad (4)$$

$$\Delta u(N) = u_{max}(N) - u_{min}(N) \quad (5)$$

As the crack propagates, the crack opening increases and consequently Δu , corresponding to a loss of stiffness, K . According to this criterion, when the stiffness drop reaches a given value, the material is considered to have failed, and the number of cycles is recorded. Since the magnitude of the stiffness of a specimen depends on several factors such as material, geometry, loading, etc., it is best practice to use a normalised stiffness defined as:

$$K_n(N) = \frac{K(N)}{K(N_0)} \cdot 100 [\%] \quad (6)$$

where N_0 is a given number of cycles chosen according to two conditions:

- The cyclic load must be stable and at the target load.
- The value of the normalisation stiffness $K(N_0)$ must not be decreasing due to the propagating fatigue crack. This is not always possible; for example, the stiffness of coach-peel specimens, due to their geometry, could decrease from the beginning of the test. In this case, N_0 is chosen as close as possible to the beginning of the test but ensuring that the first condition is met.

For each test the following steps are performed:

- The stiffness $K(N)$, calculated from the raw load and displacement data recorded during the test according to Eq. 3, is filtered by applying a rolling median (cyan points in FIGURE 6);
- The resulting stiffness data is normalised according to Eq. 6;
- The normalised stiffness, $K_n(N)$, of the lap-shear tests is then approximated using a least squares polynomial fit (blue line in FIGURE 6a). The aforementioned polynomial fit is not

able to accurately approximate $K_n(N)$ for the coach-peel tests and therefore, $K_n(N)$ obtained from the raw test data is used instead (FIGURE 6b);

- At this point, the number of cycles corresponding to the selected value of stiffness drop is extracted.

FIGURE 6 Representative examples of normalised stiffness vs cycles plots for (a) lap-shear and (b) coach-peel tests.

When the most appropriate failure criterion and the most suitable method of the two proposed earlier in this paper are identified, a series of load-life (LN) datapoints can be produced through a series of physical testing of hybrid joint specimens. The joints should be as representative as possible of the production parts, in terms of material, thickness, manufacturing process, etc. Moreover, the tests should aim to generate a set of LN datapoints evenly spread within the cycle to failure range of interest (e.g. from 10^4 to 10^6 cycles). The LN datapoints can then be reverse-engineered into stress-life (SN) datapoints through a FE analysis of the performed tests by calculating the peel stress range, $\Delta\sigma_{\text{peel}}$, through linear superposition as follows:

$$\Delta\sigma_{\text{peel}} = \sigma_{\text{peel_max_unit load}} \cdot \Delta F = \sigma_{\text{peel_max_unit load}} \cdot F_{\text{max}} \cdot (1 - R) \quad (7)$$

where $\sigma_{\text{peel_max_unit load}}$ is the maximum peel stress, obtained from the FE model (with a unit load applied), at the centroid of the membrane shell elements wrapped around the solid elements modelling the adhesive (the element experiencing the highest peel stress is likely to correspond to the failure initiation location). F_{max} is the maximum of the sinusoidal load applied in each test, and $R = F_{\text{min}}/F_{\text{max}}$ is the load ratio. Finally, through statistical analysis of the SN datapoints, it is possible to derive mean (50% certainty of survival, 50% confidence interval) and design (e.g. 97.7% certainty of survival, 95% confidence interval) SN curves together with the corresponding fatigue parameters, ready to use in nCode DesignLife.

Fatigue tests on both lap-shear and coach-peel hybrid joint specimens (adhesive + SPRs) were performed at Hottinger Brüel & Kjær’s ‘Advanced Materials Characterisation & Testing’ laboratory in the United Kingdom in collaboration with the electric vehicle manufacturer, NIO Performance Engineering Ltd. Since the second step of the second method is simply a standard spot welded/riveted joints fatigue analysis, in the remainder of this section, the data obtained from the tests is used to illustrate the process described above for the first proposed method (or the first step of the second method). Both lap-shear and coach-peel specimens were tested at ambient conditions under sinusoidal axial loading. An example of the test set-up is shown in FIGURE 7. Dimensions of the specimens and materials cannot be disclosed for confidentiality reasons.

FIGURE 7 Test set-up for (a) lap-shear and (b) coach-peel specimens.

From FIGURE 6a it can be noticed that the stiffness of the lap-shear specimen remained reasonably constant for a portion of the tests, before rapidly decreasing to a new constant stiffness level before the final stiffness drop at specimen failure. This is in agreement with the findings of other research works ([2] and [3]). By analysing the recording of the tests, it was confirmed that the first stiffness decrease corresponded to crack initiation and propagation in the adhesive until the crack reached the mechanical joints (complete failure of the adhesive). After this, the load is carried just by the mechanical joints until final failure (second stiffness drop). An example of this failure mechanism is presented in FIGURE 8 showing cohesive failure of the adhesive, until the crack reached the rivets, followed by crack initiation and propagation through one of the adherends. A similar behaviour can be observed for the coach-peel specimen, with the main difference being that the stiffness of the specimen decreased from the beginning of the test. This is typical for coach-peel specimens due to their more flexible geometry. In this case, from the analysis of the recording of the tests, it was observed that the appearance of the first visible crack on the bond line corresponded to the first significant slope change in the stiffness vs life plot (between 20% and 40% stiffness drop in FIGURE 6b). Then the crack propagated until it reached the mechanical joints approximately at the end of the first stiffness step (about 87.5% stiffness drop in FIGURE 6b). After this, similar to the lap-shear specimen, the load was carried just by the mechanical joints until final failure.

FIGURE 8 Example of failed specimen.

As mentioned above, for illustration purposes, the first method was adopted and therefore, the hybrid joints were treated as purely adhesive joints. Furthermore 5% and 40% stiffness drop were selected as the failure criteria for lap-shear and coach-peel specimens, respectively. These failure criteria are not as conservative as first visible crack appearance (as shown in FIGURE 6, at these stiffness drops cracks are already propagating in the adhesive), but they ensure acceptable residual life of the joints. However, this choice is purely arbitrary and different failure criteria can be chosen based on the users' needs. The results of the multiple fatigue tests at varying loads are shown in FIGURE 9. In particular, FIGURE 9a summarises the LN datapoints obtained from the analysis of the test data for the chosen failure criteria. FIGURE 9b, instead, shows the SN datapoints obtained by reverse-engineering the LN datapoints using Eq. 7, and the corresponding regression lines (SN curves). The fatigue parameters describing the two SN curves cannot be disclosed for confidentiality reasons. FIGURE 9a also shows that, as expected, lap-shear joints can withstand higher fatigue loads than coach-peel joints, as the same applied load produces significantly higher peel stresses along the bond line of coach-peel specimens compared to lap-shear specimens. For the case study presented in this paper, this led to the SN curve for the coach-peel joints being above the SN curve for the lap-shear joints. This highlights further the importance of generating the joint models by testing specimens that are as representative as possible of the joints in the production parts and using the same meshing strategy and constitutive model used to model and design the production components.

FIGURE 9 Experimental load-life datapoints (a) and reverse-engineered SN datapoints with corresponding regression lines (b). The plots have been anonymised for confidentiality reasons.

CONCLUSIONS

This paper introduces two practical methodologies for the fatigue life prediction of hybrid joints that companies, especially in the automotive industry, can easily implement with relatively limited modifications to the typical FE modelling strategies used today. The FE modelling guidelines proposed in this paper allow to generate reasonably mesh insensitive models that are not computationally too onerous, and that do not require congruent meshes.

The first method is based on the simplifying and conservative assumption of neglecting the life of the mechanical joints after the failure of the adhesive. According to this assumption, the hybrid joint is treated as a purely adhesive joint. The peel stresses, to be used as input to perform fatigue analyses using the DesignLife standard SN Analysis Engine, can be efficiently recovered along the bond-lines by following the proposed FE modelling guidelines.

The second method is an extension of the first method, and it considers the life of the hybrid joint as the sum of the lives of both the adhesive and the mechanical joints.

The first method is more economical from both a modelling and computational point of view, but it might produce over-conservative fatigue life predictions. The second method, instead, would produce more realistic fatigue life estimations compared to the first method, but at higher modelling and computational costs, as it requires two separate analyses to estimate the fatigue lives of the adhesive and the mechanical joints. Specifically, the fatigue life of the adhesive is estimated through the first method, while the fatigue life of the mechanical joints is estimated through a standard spot welded/riveted joints fatigue analysis as described in the nCode DesignLife Theory Guide [13].

A convergence study of the FE modelling strategy proposed for the first method (or the first step of the second method) was performed for both lap-shear and coach-peel specimen geometries. This showed that the use of membrane shell elements ‘bonded’ to the free faces of the solid elements used to model the adhesive (i.e. along the bond-line), is a valid solution to recover the peel stresses from the solid elements, with a good level of mesh insensitivity.

Moreover, a process to derive bespoke fatigue parameters of the hybrid joints through physical testing was described and applied to a real case study. From the analysis of the test data a two-stage evolution the stiffness was observed during the tests of both lap-shear and coach-peel specimens. In particular, a first stage corresponding to the crack initiation and propagation in the adhesive layer until complete failure of the adhesive (when the crack reaches the mechanical joints), is followed by a second stage, where only the mechanical joints carry the load and contribute to the fatigue life of the joint.

As a final remark, since the whole approach presented in this paper is based on the concept of similitude, it is fundamental that the tested specimens are as representative as possible of the joints in the production parts, and that the meshing strategy and the constitutive model used to derive the joint model(s) coincide with those used to model and design the production components. This was further highlighted by the results of the case study.

The results presented in this paper are part of an extensive testing programme currently underway at Hottinger Brüel & Kjær’s ‘Advanced Materials Characterisation & Testing’ laboratory in the United Kingdom, in collaboration with the electric vehicle manufacturer, NIO Performance Engineering Ltd. The test programme involves hybrid joints made using various parent materials, thicknesses, and mechanical joining techniques. The full set of results generated at the end of the testing programme will be used to further validate the proposed method. Furthermore, they will be used to generate the final SN curves, enhance the simulation capability, and therefore, ensure the structural integrity of NIO vehicle body architecture. Finally, a further step would be to apply the proposed approach to full structures, such as vehicles body-in-white for further validation.

ACKNOWLEDGMENTS

The Authors would like to thank NIO Performance Engineering Ltd for the collaboration. We also thank Alex Pierpoint and Jeffrey Mentley from Hottinger Bruel & Kjaer for their kind support on specimen preparation, testing, and valuable discussions on modelling methods.

REFERENCE LIST

- (1) Abdel Wahab, M. M., *Int. Sch. Res. Notices*, Vol. 2012, 2012, pp. 1–25.
- (2) Moroni, F., *J. Adhes.*, Vol. 95, No. 5–7, 2019, pp. 577–594.
- (3) Wu, G., Li, D., Lai, W.-J., Shi, Y., Kang, H., Peng, Y., and Su, X., *Int. J. Fatigue*, Vol. 142, 2021, 105948.

- (4) Sun, X., Stephens, E. V., and Khaleel, M. A., *Int. J. Fatigue*, Vol. 29, No. 2, 2007, pp. 370–386.
- (5) Yang, B., Shan, H., Liang, Y., Ma, Y., Niu, S., Zhu, X., and Li, Y., *J. Mater. Process. Technol.*, Vol. 299, 2022, 117336.
- (6) Lai, W. J., and Pan, J., *Int. J. Fatigue*, Vol. 75, 2015, pp. 184–197.
- (7) Al-Samhan, A., and Darwish, S. M. H., *J. Mater. Process. Technol.*, Vol. 142, 2003, pp. 587–598.
- (8) Al-Samhan, A. M., *J. King Saud Univ. – Eng. Sci.*, Vol. 18, No. 1, 2005, pp. 57–65.
- (9) Sadowski, T., Golewski, P., and Zarzeka-Raczkowska, E., *Comput. Mater. Sci.*, Vol. 50, No. 4, 2011, pp. 1256–1262.
- (10) Sadowski, T., and Zarzeka-Raczkowska, E., *Arch. Metall. Mater.*, Vol. 57, No. 4, 2012, pp. 1127–1135.
- (11) Fricke, H., and Vallée, T., *J. Adhes.*, Vol. 92, No. 7–9, 2016, pp. 652–664.
- (12) Heyes, P., Björkman, G., Blows, A., Mumford, T., and Briskham, P., *SAE Int. J. Mater. Manuf.*, Vol. 5, No. 1, 2012, pp. 215–225.
- (13) Hottinger Brüel & Kjær, *DesignLife Fatigue Theory Guide*, 2023.